

Tsallis Entropy from Maximization of Entropy and the Condition of Stability Part 3

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In the note, we argue that statistical mechanics, at least with respect to Boltzmann/Shannon entropy and Tsallis entropy, may be formulated strictly through information related to $-ei/T$ considerations. In fact, as argued in Part 2, there is no need for any notion of maximization of entropy subject to constraints or even reaction balance in the case of Shannon's entropy. We suggest that by beginning with the general statement: $F(p(ei)) = -ei/T$, (which means simply that F inverse = p), the entire focus is on the relation between F , $p(ei)$ and ei/T .

In Part 2, we considered the a priori first moment constraint: $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } ei \text{ } p(ei)$ for the Shannon case and $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } ei \text{ } p(ei)^q$ for Tsallis. Here we show that any order moment yields the same result in the information scheme, whereas this is not the case in an extremization problem.

As a result, we suggest that the Shannon and Tsallis theories follow from information (concerning $-ei/T$) considerations. In the Shannon case, one finds that these considerations lead to a solution with an interesting property: $p(e1)p(e2) = p(e1+e2)$. In other words, even though $p(ei)$ carries direct information about ei , it does not encode any further special features, so that $p(e1)p(e2) = p(ei)p(ej)$ if $e1+e2 = ei+ej$. This, we argue, is the notion of maximum number of states in the Shannon case, but this does not hold in the Tsallis. Thus, we suggest that perhaps one should not consider statistical mechanics as focusing on maximizing the number of states, but rather focus on information considerations.

Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) Distribution

We have argued in previous notes that one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution (linked to Shannon's entropy) in two ways. The first is by maximizing the \ln of the number of states, where:

$$1/\text{number of states} = \text{Product over } i \text{ } p(ei)^{Np(ei)} \text{ for } N \text{ large} \quad ((1))$$

Extremizing \ln of ((1)) subject to the a priori constraints: $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(ei) = 1$ and $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } ei \text{ } p(ei) = E_{\text{total}}$ yields the MB distribution: $C \exp(-ei/T)$.

One issue that may arise with this approach is the insistence on using the first moment as the constraint, i.e.

$$\text{Sum over } ei \text{ } p(ei) = E_{\text{total}} \quad ((2))$$

One might ask: Why cannot one use higher moments, e.g. $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(ei) \text{ } ei^n = \text{constant}(n)$? ((3))

One may at first note that if a set of N particles with a total energy of E_{total} are placed in a box, then it is only the first moment that is known, and not the others. There is no a priori constraint on the second or higher moments. Alternatively, however, one may take a gas at equilibrium and

measure $p(e_i)$ and well as any moment ((3)). Thus, one may actually find the numbers for the various moments for the equilibrium gas and ask: What is wrong with extremizing:

$$- \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) + B_1 \sum_i p(e_i) + B_2 \sum_i e_i p(e_i) ? \quad ((4))$$

Unfortunately, one obtains a different answer depending on which moment-constraints one uses. It would be nice to have a method which does not have this problem and we argue that the information $(-e_i/T)$ approach is one such method.

The second approach to finding $C \exp(-e_i/T)$ is to use reaction balance:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{with} \quad p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \quad ((5b))$$

Taking \ln of ((5b)) and equating to ((5a)) yields: $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ or $p(e_i)$ unnormalized = $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

We argue that in this approach, the key idea is still that there exists a function:

$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and one we show in the next section that one needs neither extremization of entropy nor reaction balance to find the MB distribution.

Information $(-e_i/T)$ Approach to Finding Distributions

We suggest that the key focus of finding $p(e_i)$ is based on examining its relationship to $-e_i/T$, which we call relevant information. We begin with the simple, general statement:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((6)) \quad F \text{ is simply the inverse function of } p(e_i) \text{ and both are unknown.}$$

Here $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized.

The point of writing ((6)) is that the entire focus of the analysis is on the relationship between F , p and the information $-e_i/T$. ((6)) provides no solution, but we argued in Parts I and 2 that one should also consider an a priori constraint in the problem. In particular, we chose the first moment:

$$\sum_i e_i p_1(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$$

where $p_1(e_i)$ is normalized. ((7)) We then multiplied ((6)) by $p(e_i)$ and took the derivative $d/dp(e_i)$ arguing that the second term, $p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i) = 1$ because all of the $-e_i/T$ information is contained in $(dp(e_i)/dp(e_i)) F(p(e_i))$, i.e. the first term.

We now note that one may use any moment one wishes, unlike the extremization approach.

For example, consider the constraint $\sum_i e_i^n p_1(e_i)$. Then:

$$F(p(e_i)) \text{ power } n = (-e_i/T) \text{ power } n \quad ((7))$$

and one multiplies by $p(e_i)$, the probability used to establish an average-like structure.

One may then take $d/dp(e_i)$ of the LHS to obtain:

$$F(p(e_i)) \text{ power } n + p(e_i) n F(e_i) \text{ power } (n-1) dF/dp$$

The first term contains all information regarding $-e_i/T$, so the second term should be a constant. Thus,

$$p(e_i) n (-e_i/T) \text{ power } (n-1) dF/dp = \text{constant} \rightarrow p(e_i) dF/dp = \text{constant say } 1 \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is then a general statement which applies to all moments, i.e. to any n . We suggest that the information $(-e_i/T)$ approach is general.

In the Tsallis case, $p_1(e_i) \text{ power } q$ instead of $p_1(e_i)$ appears in averages of moments so one again considers ((6)) to a power n , but this time multiplied by $p(e_i) \text{ power } q$:

$$p(e_i) \text{ power } q \{ F(p(e_i)) \text{ power } n \} = p(e_i) \text{ power } q (-e_i/T) \text{ power } n \quad ((9))$$

The $d/dp(e_i)$ derivative acting on the first factor of the LHS of ((9)) yields all of the $-e_i/T$ information, so:

$$p(e_i) \text{ power } q n (F(p(e_i)) \text{ power } (n-1) dF/dp = \text{constant or: } p(e_i) \text{ power } q dF/dp = 1 \text{ for any } n.$$

Again, any n yields the same result. If one insists that for $q=1$, $F(p) = \ln(p)$, then as shown in Parts 1 and 2,

$$F(p) = \ln(p) = \{ p \text{ power } (1-q) - 1 \} / \{1-q\} \text{ and } p(e_i) = \{1 - (1-q) e_i/T\} \text{ power } 1/(1-q) \quad ((10))$$

As a result, no extremization of entropy subject to constraints or reaction balance is needed.

The Situation of Maximizing the Number of States

We note that in the information $(-e_i/T)$ approach, no mention is made of the number of states or the maximization of this number. We point out, however, that for $p_1(e_i)$ being used as the weight for $e_i \text{ power } n$ in a constraint:

$$F(p) = \ln(p) \quad ((11))$$

$$\text{Thus: } \ln(p(e_1)) + \ln(p(e_2)) = \ln(p(e_1)p(e_2)) \rightarrow p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_i)p(e_j) \text{ if } e_1+e_2=e_i+e_j \quad ((12))$$

In other words, $p(e_i)$ carries information about $-e_i/T$, but otherwise the function does not provide any unique feature which treats one e_i differently than another. We argue that ((12)) is a special case as this property does not hold for the Tsallis situation. We argue that ((12)) is linked with any $\{e_i\}$ set such that one has E_{total} carrying the same weight. This is the maximization of states, but we do not use it a priori because it only arises in the special case of ((11)). We suggest that this is a relevant point because there seems to be a tendency in the literature to try to maximize the number of states a priori. We suggest rather that statistical mechanics seems to be based on $-e_i/T$ considerations which may or may not be linked with a maximum number of states.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one does not need to consider either maximization of entropy subject to constraints or reaction balance in order to determine statistical distributions. We suggest instead an information based on an $-e_i/T$ approach which begins with $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, i.e. F is simply the inverse of p . Unlike the extremization of entropy case, where different moment constraints yield different distributions, the information $-e_i/T$ approach yields the same result for any moment.

We argue that one writes: $p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ power n (if $p(e_i)$ is the probability weight as in the Shannon case) or $p(e_i)$ power q $F(p(e_i))$ power n , as in the Tsallis. We then take $d/dp(e_i)$ with the first term representing all of the $-e_i/T$ information present such that the second term should be a constant. Thus: $n p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ power $(n-1) dF/dp = \text{constant} \rightarrow p dF/dp = 1$ (choosing 1 here) and $n p(e_i)$ power q $F(p)$ power $(n-1) dF/dp = \text{constant} \rightarrow p$ power q $dF/dp = 1$ for the Tsallis case. This yields F and p and one may even create an entropy function.

We note that in the special case of $p(e_i)$ being used as the probability weight, $F(p) = \ln(p)$ which implies that: $\ln(p(e_1)p(e_2)) = \ln(p(e_i)p(e_j))$ if $e_1+e_2=e_i+e_j$. Thus, we argue that this special case implies a generic property to $p(e_i)$, i.e. the usual feature that any distribution or e_i with a total E_{total} carries the same weight. This is the maximization of states view, but we argue that it only appears as a special case.